

Synthesis, Characterisation and Antibacterial Activity of some 3d-Metal Complexes with Thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-chloro/bromoaniline

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Several Schiff base metal complexes have been studied in past because of their wide applicability¹. Survey of literature reveals insufficient systematic work on the Schiff base complexes of thiophene-2-aldehyde and aromatic haloanilines^{2,3}. The derivatives of such compounds as such and also after suitable structural modifications, may be used as bioactive materials. The present investigation aims at the study of the complexes of life-essential metal ions with the bioactive ligands with a view of work out systematically their biological significance.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the metal complexes (Table 1) of thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-chloro/bromoaniline indicate metal-ligand stoichiometry for all the six complexes to be 1 : 2. The conductivity data of the thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-chloroaniline (TCA) complexes in DMF (10^{-3} M) confirm the bi-bivalent electrolytic nature ($139-150 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$). The molar conductance values of thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-bromoaniline (TBA) complexes in DMF suggest non-electrolytic nature for the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes ($18-26 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$), while for the Ni^{II} complex ($161 \Omega^{-1}$

$\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) bi-bivalent electrolytic nature⁴. The observed magnetic moment values (Table 1) for all the complexes indicate the high-spin octahedral geometry.

The ir band due to azomethine group in the ligands ($1625 \pm 5 \text{cm}^{-1}$) shifted to lower frequency side ($1580 \pm 20 \text{cm}^{-1}$) in the metal complexes. The decrease in electron density over this group reflects its participation in coordination. The thiophene C-S-C band at 840cm^{-1} in the ligand has gone down by $20-40 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, suggesting its involvement in chelation. The bands due to stretching and bending vibration of water appear in the spectra of the complexes at 3440 ± 10 and $1610 \pm 10 \text{cm}^{-1}$. The coordinated mode of water molecules in the M(II)-TCA complexes has been confirmed by the appearance of rocking band at $780 \pm 20 \text{cm}^{-1}$. The new bands in the spectra of the complexes around 360 ± 10 and $500 \pm 20 \text{cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to M-S and M-N bonding respectively. The vibration of sulphate ion in M(II)-TCA complexes appears at 1100 ± 10 and $610 \pm 10 \text{cm}^{-1}$. This in association with conductance data indicate the uncoordinated nature of sulphate group. The presence of sulphate ion in coordination sphere of Co^{II} -TBA and Cu^{II} -TBA complexes has been inferred by the bands at 1030 ± 10 , 970 ± 10 and $630 \pm 10 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra^{2,3,5}.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} -TCA complex shows two bands at 16.20 and 20.40 kK corresponding to transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ respectively. The first band ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (\nu_1)$ should theoretically occur at 7.20 kK. The values of $10Dq$, B , β , ν_3/ν_2 and LFSE are 9000cm^{-1} , 1000cm^{-1} , 0.89, 1.25 and 86.18kJ mol^{-1} respectively, which are in fair agreement with the predicted values of octahedral complex. In Co^{II} -TBA complex, the bands due to characteristic ν_1 and ν_3 transitions appear at 10.70 and 23.08 kK. The ν_2 transition band could not be clearly recorded due to its very low intensity, however, its computed value comes to be 22.45 kK. The values of ligand field parameters, viz. $10Dq$, B , β , ν_3/ν_2 and LFSE are 11757, 895, 0.79, 1.02 and 112.10 respectively, which are in conformity with the octahedral geometry^{6,7}.

The absorption spectrum of Ni^{II} -TCA complex shows three bands at 10.50, 16.90 and 25.40 kK, corresponding to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow$

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES*

Compd	M p. (°C)/ (Colour)	Analysis% : Found/ (Calcd.)	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{ClNS}$ (ligand)	100-05 (Brown)	-	-	-
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{ClNS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ $\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	202-05 (Purple)	8.90 (9.00)	139	4.82
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{ClNS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ $\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	195-200 (Blue)	8.60 (8.91)	148	3.06
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{ClNS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ $\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	180-85 (Pista)	9.80 (9.00)	150	1.92
$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{BrNS}$ (ligand)	105-10 (Green)	-	-	-
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{BrNS})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	210-15 (Pink)	8.40 (7.20)	18	4.75
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{BrNS})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	206-10 (Grey)	8.30 (7.50)	161	-
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{BrNS})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	175-80 (Green)	8.70 (7.70)	26	1.88

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

${}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. The values of $10Dq$, B , β , v_3/v_2 , λ' and LFSE are 10 500, 949, 0.87, 1.50, (-)213 and 150.82 respectively. This confirms the octahedral geometry. The spectrum of Ni^{II} -TBA complex shows three bands at 13.90 (weaker), 17.80 and 26.20 kK, corresponding to transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ respectively. This supports the square-planar geometry⁷.

Cu^{II} -TCA complex spectrum shows a broad band at 13.90 kK (${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$) suggesting the octahedral geometry. The values of $10Dq$, λ' and LFSE are 13 900, (-)723 and 99.83 respectively. A single broad asymmetric band has been observed in the Cu^{II} -TBA complex at 14.62 kK (${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$). The values of $10Dq$, (14 620), λ' (-633) and LFSE (104.60) are in good agreement with the octahedral geometry of this complex^{6,7}.

The above results reveal that the Schiff bases act as bidentate ligand chelating through thiophene-S and azomethine-N.

Antimicrobial activity: Some of the compounds exhibited mild to moderate antimicrobial activity against the selected pathogenic organisms, viz. *Escherichia coli* (*E.c*), *Salmonella typhi* (*S.t*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S.a*) and *Bacillus subtilis* (*B.s*) (Table 2). The chloro series compounds showed moderate to better activity against the pathogens. In general, the Cu^{II} complexes are more effective than the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes^{3,8}.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.**	<i>E.c</i>	<i>S.t</i>	<i>S.a</i>	<i>B.s</i>
	25(50) $\mu g\ ml^{-1}$	25(50) $\mu g\ ml^{-1}$	25(50) $\mu g\ ml^{-1}$	25(50) $\mu g\ ml^{-1}$
$C_{11}H_8CINS$	B(C)	B(B)	B(C)	B(C)
$Co(TCA)_2(H_2O)_2 \cdot SO_4 \cdot H_2O$	A(B)	B(B)	B(C)	B(C)
$Ni(TCA)_2(H_2O)_2 \cdot SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	B(C)	A(B)	-(A)	C(D)
$Cu(TCA)_2(H_2O)_2 \cdot SO_4 \cdot H_2O$	C(D)	C(C)	C(D)	B(D)
$C_{11}H_8BrNS$	-	A(B)	-(A)	A(B)
$Co(TBA)_2 \cdot SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	-	-	-(A)	-(A)
$Ni(TBA)_2 \cdot SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	-	A(B)	-	-(A)
$Cu(TBA)_2 \cdot SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	B(C)	A(B)	-(A)	A(B)
Streptomycin	B(C)	C(D)	B(C)	C(D)

*Zone of inhibition : (A) = 5–8 mm; (B) = 8–13 mm; (C) = 13–20 mm; (D) = 20–28 mm; (-) = not measurable.

**TCA = Thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-chloroaniline; TBA = thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-bromoaniline.

Experimental

The Schiff bases (ligands) were synthesised by refluxing an equimolar amount of thiophene-2-aldehyde and 4-chloro/bromoaniline in methanolic medium on a water-bath for 4–5 h. The resulting product was of greenish brown colour.

The metal complex was prepared by refluxing a mixture of methanolic solutions of the metal salt $MSO_4 \cdot nH_2O$ (0.01 mol) and thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-chloro/bromoaniline (0.02 mol) on a water-bath for 4–6 h. The coloured precipitate that appeared on cooling the solution, was dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a dessicator and also in an electric oven at 80°.

M.p. was determined on a Toshniwal apparatus. Electronic spectra (MeOH) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 2B spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on an Acculab 10 spectrophotometer (at C.D.R.I., Lucknow). Magnetic measurement was done at room temperature (306 K) by the Gouy's technique. Conductance was measured on an Elico-CM82 conductivity bridge. The purity of the compounds was monitored by tlc on silica gel plates.

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